

SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE PRESERVATION AND RESTORATION OF KHIVA MINARETS USING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES (ICT)

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ABSTRACT

For the first time, schematic drawings of minarets have been prepared using advanced modern technologies with the assistance of ICT (Information and Communication Technologies). Not all minarets in Khiva have been artistically decorated with tiles; we will focus on certain minarets where tilework has been applied, as well as minarets in a state of disrepair

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For ICT to be effective in education, it must be fully integrated¹ into architecture; specifically, using ICT alongside writing for teaching literacy and mathematics yields better results than traditional methods or ICT alone². The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), a division of the United Nations, has integrated ICT into education as part of its efforts to ensure equality and access to educational opportunities. The following, taken directly from UNESCO's publication on educational ICT, explains the organization's position on this initiative.

Information and communication technologies can contribute to universal access to education, equity in education, quality teaching and learning, professional development of teachers, and more effective educational management, governance, and administration. UNESCO applies a holistic and comprehensive approach to promoting ICT in education. Access, inclusion, and quality are among the key issues they can address. The organization's intersectoral platform on ICT in education focuses on these issues through the collaborative activities of its three sectors: communication and information, education, and science³.

¹ "Yozuv o'qishni qanday yaxshilashi mumkinligi haqida dalillar, Carnegie.Org 2010"

² Genlott, Annika Agélii; Grönlund, Åke (August 2016). "Bo'shliqlarni yopish-AKT-kengaytirilgan hamkorlik orqali savodxonlik va matematikani yaxshilash". *Kompyuterlar Va Ta'lim*. 99: 68–80. doi:10.1016 / j. compedu.2016.04.004

³ "Ta'limda AKT". YUNESKO. Olindi10 Qadam2016.

Despite the power of computers to improve and reform teaching and learning practices, improper implementation is a widespread issue⁴ beyond funding and technological achievements, with little evidence that teachers and tutors are correctly integrating ICT into daily education. Internal barriers such as belief in traditional teaching practices and individual attitudes toward computers in education, as well as teachers' comfort with computers and their ability to use them effectively, result in varying degrees of effectiveness in ICT integration into the classroom⁵.

Regarding the preservation and restoration of Khiva minarets using Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), scholars from the Khorezm Ma'mun Academy have created an electronic database of architectural monuments in the city of Khiva, incorporating comprehensive materials on the history and technical condition of tangible cultural heritage sites. During the process of forming the electronic database, as a result of comprehensive studies to determine the technical condition of historical architectural monuments located in the Ichan Kala and Dishan Kala territories of Khiva city, the research results of scholars and materials from the electronic database were also used in developing the program for implementing the international project "Ichan Kala - World Heritage Site" included in UNESCO's World Heritage List, and it can be seen that they were applied in the conservation and restoration of 94 historical architectural monuments of Khiva city.

The electronic database, created in catalog form, contains information about the history of each monument in the city, their dimensions, current technical condition and equipment, and the materials used in their construction. All of this is accompanied by relevant photographs⁶.

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⁴ Birt, Jaklin; Safari, Maryam; De Kastro, Vinsent Bikudo (2023-03-20). "Buxgalteriya o'quv dasturiga AKT va ma'lumotlar tahlilining integratsiyasini tanqidiy tahlil qilish: ko'p o'lchovli istiqbol". *Buxgalteriya Hisobi Va Moliya*. 63 (4): 4037–4063. doi:10.1111 / acfi.13084. ISSN 0810-5391. S2CID 257675501.

⁵ Blekvell, K. K., Lauricella, A. R. va Vartella, E., 2014. Erta bolalik ta'limida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar. *Kompyuterlar va ta'lim*, 77, 82-90 betlar.

⁶ <https://uza.uz/posts/417631>

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